

EEG Signal Processing Pipeline for Enhanced Model Performance

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1 Abstract

This study investigates the impact of different preprocessing techniques on EEG signal classification using a CNN-BiLSTM model. Using the inherently noisy BCI Competition 2008–Graz dataset A, we applied Independent Component Analysis (ICA) to all files for artifact removal. Additionally, Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR) was applied selectively: once across all files and another time only for the noisiest subjects. The effect of epoching before applying ICA and ASR was also analyzed. While ASR showed limited impact when applied only to the noisiest subjects, its application across the entire dataset slightly improved performance. A refined CNN-BiLSTM architecture was developed to handle non-stationary signals more effectively. We also explored the role of bias initialization in BiLSTM units, though it was not the primary focus of this study. Our results highlight the importance of optimal preprocessing, careful epoching, and model design in improving EEG classification performance for brain-computer interface (BCI) tasks.

2 Introduction

Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) provide a direct communication pathway between the brain and external devices, enabling control without traditional motor outputs. Applications of BCIs span various fields, including assistive technologies for individuals with severe motor disabilities, rehabilitation for stroke patients, and even gaming and entertainment. By translating neural signals into actionable commands, BCIs empower users to interact with their environment in innovative ways, offering significant potential for enhancing quality of life and expanding human capabilities.

Electroencephalography (EEG) is widely used in BCI systems due to its non-invasive nature, capturing electrical activity from the scalp. However, working with EEG data presents several key challenges that hinder effective signal classification:

1. **Low Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR):** EEG signals are often weak and contaminated by noise from non-neuronal sources, such as muscle activity and eye movements. This contamination leads to a low SNR, complicating the extraction of meaningful brain signals. Effective preprocessing techniques, including Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR), can enhance the SNR by removing artifacts and reconstructing cleaner signal subspaces.
2. **Non-Stationarity of EEG Signals:** The dynamic nature of EEG signals results in significant changes over time, both within and across recording sessions. This non-stationarity challenges machine learning models, as the signal patterns shift unpredictably, resulting in classification inconsistencies. Implementing proper epoching and baseline correction before applying preprocessing methods can stabilize the signal, enabling more reliable classification.
3. **Individual Differences in EEG Signals Across Subjects:** EEG signals exhibit considerable variability between individuals due to differences in brain anatomy and cognitive processes. This inter-subject variability complicates the generalization of machine learning models, leading to performance drops when applying the same model across different subjects. A comprehensive preprocessing pipeline that incorporates ICA and ASR can help create more consistent and generalizable features, thereby mitigating the effects of individual differences.

To address these challenges, the following preprocessing methods are employed:

- **Independent Component Analysis (ICA):** ICA decomposes EEG signals into independent components, allowing for the identification and removal of artifacts such as eye blinks and muscle movements. This technique is effective across various datasets, enhancing the clarity of the signals.
- **Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR):** ASR filters out transient noise by reconstructing the signal subspace associated with artifacts. This technique is most effective when applied to the entire dataset rather than selectively on noisy segments, as it helps maintain the integrity of the signal during reconstruction.
- **Epoching and Baseline Correction:** Proper epoching involves segmenting the data into time windows, while baseline correction reduces non-stationary effects. Implementing these steps before applying ICA and ASR ensures better data quality, facilitating improved model training and performance.

While alternative solutions, such as invasive techniques like intracranial EEG (iEEG) and electrocorticography (ECoG), can address some of these challenges by providing higher SNR and spatial resolution, this research focuses on the non-invasive nature of EEG due to its accessibility and lower risk to participants.

In this research, we apply these preprocessing techniques to the BCI Competition 2008–Graz dataset A, which is inherently noisy and non-stationary. We evaluate their effectiveness using a CNN-BiLSTM architecture designed to capture EEG signal dynamics and account for inter-subject variability.

Additionally, we will briefly discuss the significance of bias initialization in the forget gate of BiLSTM units, as proper initialization can influence the model’s ability to retain important information over time. Although this aspect is secondary to our primary focus on preprocessing methods, it contributes to the overall performance of the model.

Our goal is to identify the optimal preprocessing pipeline that can improve classification accuracy by addressing the low SNR, non-stationarity, and individual differences in EEG signals.

3 Related Work

Prior research has significantly advanced the field of EEG preprocessing techniques, including methods such as Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR) and Independent Component Analysis (ICA), which are pivotal for improving signal quality before classification.

3.1 EEG Preprocessing Techniques

Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR) has been shown to effectively remove transient artifacts from EEG data. As discussed in several studies, ASR reconstructs the signal subspace associated with artifacts, thus preserving the underlying brain activity while enhancing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [1, 2]. Research indicates that ASR outperforms traditional methods in various scenarios, particularly in real-time applications [3].

Independent Component Analysis (ICA) is another widely used technique that separates EEG signals into independent sources. Studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in isolating and removing artifacts such as eye movements and muscle activity, thereby improving classification outcomes [4, 5]. However, ICA's effectiveness is contingent on careful component selection and validation, as misclassification can lead to erroneous results.

3.2 Machine Learning Models for EEG Classification

Recent advancements have seen the adoption of sophisticated machine learning models for EEG classification, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs).

3.2.1 CNN-LSTM Models

CNNs are adept at capturing spatial features from EEG signals, while LSTMs effectively model temporal dependencies [6]. Studies have shown that combining CNNs and LSTMs enhances classification accuracy by leveraging both spatial and temporal characteristics of the EEG data [7].

3.2.2 Bias Initialization in LSTMs

Bias initialization in LSTM units has been explored in various studies to enhance model performance. Proper initialization of biases in the forget gate helps retain critical information over time, addressing the vanishing gradient problem [8]. Research indicates that different initialization strategies can significantly influence model convergence and overall effectiveness [9].

4 Methodology

In our research, we build upon these foundational techniques to establish a robust EEG classification framework. We focus on the following aspects:

4.1 Preprocessing Pipeline

We employ ASR and ICA for preprocessing the BCI Competition 2008–Graz dataset A, ensuring enhanced SNR and reduced artifacts. A comprehensive evaluation of preprocessing effectiveness will be conducted by comparing classification results across various methods. We will also conduct extensive experiments to demonstrate the significant effects of both ASR and ICA, along with proper epoching.

4.2 Model Architecture

We utilize a novel hybrid CNN-BiLSTM architecture to capture both spatial and temporal features of the EEG signals. This new architecture enables us to exploit the advantages of both CNNs and BiLSTMs in handling complex EEG data.

4.3 Bias Initialization

We will investigate various bias initialization strategies for the forget gate in BiLSTM units to assess their impact on model performance. Our objective is to identify optimal configurations that enhance the retention of critical information.

By integrating advanced preprocessing techniques with robust machine learning models, we aim to improve classification accuracy and provide insights into effective strategies for tackling the inherent challenges of EEG data.

4.4 Dataset

In this study, we utilize the BCI Competition 2008 – Graz dataset A [10], which consists of data collected from **nine subjects** performing motor imagery tasks. Each subject’s EEG data includes recordings from **22 EEG channels** along with additional channels for eye movement artifacts. The classification tasks involve distinguishing between various motor imagery tasks, such as imagining left-hand movement, right-hand movement, foot movement, and tongue movement. This dataset provides a challenging yet rich resource for exploring EEG signal processing and machine learning techniques. For a detailed description of the dataset, please refer to the provided citation.

4.5 Preprocessing Techniques

We employed five distinct preprocessing pipelines in our experiments, as follows:

- **Experiment 1:** ICA without ASR.
- **Experiment 2:** ICA with ASR (applied to noisy files only).
- **Experiment 3:** No epoching before ICA.
- **Experiment 4:** ICA and ASR applied to all files.
- **Experiment 5:** ICA, ASR, and different bias initialization for the BiLSTM forget gate.

These experiments aim to evaluate the impact of various preprocessing techniques on classification performance, highlighting the importance of effective signal conditioning.

4.6 CNN-BiLSTM Model Architecture

For our analysis, we employed a fixed CNN-BiLSTM-CNN-BiLSTM architecture across all experiments. This model was chosen for its ability to effectively capture both spatial and temporal features of the EEG signals. The convolutional layers (CNN) extract spatial patterns from the EEG data, while the bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) layers are used to model temporal dependencies in both forward and backward directions, enhancing the model’s ability to learn complex patterns in the time-series data more comprehensively. The bidirectional nature of the BiLSTMs allows the model to capture information from the entire sequence, improving its performance on tasks involving long-term dependencies.

In Experiment 5, we specifically altered the bias initialization of the BiLSTM forget gate. In all previous experiments, the bias for the forget gate was initialized to 1, which helped the model retain more information over time. However, in Experiment 5, we set the forget gate bias to 0 to evaluate the impact of this change on model performance. The results indicated that initializing the forget gate to 0 led to lower performance compared to a bias of 1, suggesting that retaining more information over time with a bias of 1 was more beneficial for this task. This highlights the importance of proper bias initialization in handling long-term dependencies in LSTM networks.

5 Experiments

The dataset was divided into training, validation, and test sets with an 81-9-10 split, ensuring a robust evaluation of the model’s performance. We performed mean centering on the training set and applied the same mean to the validation and test sets. This approach mitigated biases and ensured consistent data representation across all subsets. Finally, we utilized StandardScaler for further normalization of the training data, ensuring that the model could learn effectively from the standardized inputs. Hyperparameters were set as follows:

- **Batch Size:** 100
- **Learning Rate:** 0.0007
- **Weight Decay:** 0.002
- **Number of Epochs:** 250

The training phase involved using cross-entropy loss to optimize the model, with training and validation accuracy monitored throughout to evaluate model performance and detect potential overfitting. The model’s performance was further assessed using a separate test dataset after training was complete

5.1 Model Architecture

The CNN-BiLSTM-CNN-BiLSTM model architecture employed in this study was designed to leverage both spatial and temporal features from the EEG data. The architecture can be summarized as follows:

1. **First Convolutional Layer:** The model begins with a convolutional layer that captures spatial features from the EEG data. This layer applies convolutional filters to extract relevant patterns and characteristics from the input time-series data.
2. **First BiLSTM Layer:** Following the initial convolutional layer, a bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) layer is integrated. This layer is particularly effective for sequential data like EEG signals, as it captures long-term dependencies and temporal patterns in both forward and backward directions.
3. **Second Convolutional Layer:** Another convolutional layer follows the first BiLSTM, further refining the extracted features and enhancing the model’s ability to recognize complex patterns.
4. **Second BiLSTM Layer:** The architecture then includes a second BiLSTM layer, which continues to model the temporal dependencies in the EEG signals. This repeated structure helps the model to better learn and retain critical information across different time steps.
5. **Bias Initialization:** In Experiment 5, special attention was given to the bias initialization of the BiLSTM forget gate. Proper initialization is crucial for the model’s performance, as it can influence how the BiLSTM learns over time. This experiment aimed to investigate the impact of different bias initializations on the forget gate, evaluating how it affects model performance in conjunction with the preprocessing techniques.
6. **Fully Connected Layers:** After the final BiLSTM layer, fully connected (dense) layers are included, which take the high-level features extracted by the convolutional and BiLSTM layers and map them to the final output classes.
7. **Output Layer:** The model concludes with a softmax output layer that provides class probabilities, allowing for multi-class classification of the EEG signals.

This CNN-BiLSTM-CNN-BiLSTM architecture was chosen due to its ability to effectively combine both spatial feature extraction and temporal sequence modeling, making it well-suited for the challenges associated with EEG classification tasks.

5.2 Preprocessing Techniques

The five preprocessing pipelines were implemented as follows:

1. **Experiment 1:** ICA was performed without ASR, allowing us to analyze the impact of ICA alone on the EEG signals.
2. **Experiment 2:** ICA was applied to all files, while ASR was specifically combined with ICA only for the noisy files, namely A04T and A09T. This experiment aimed to assess the effectiveness of ASR in removing artifacts from these particular datasets.
3. **Experiment 3:** No epoching was applied before ICA, resulting in raw data being processed directly. This approach aimed to evaluate how the model handles unprocessed signals, providing insight into the necessity of epoching in EEG data preprocessing.
4. **Experiment 4:** ICA and ASR were applied to all files, providing a comprehensive evaluation of their combined effectiveness across the dataset.
5. **Experiment 5:** This pipeline included ICA, ASR, and bias initialization for the BiLSTM forget gate. This experiment aimed to understand how bias initialization influences model performance in conjunction with the preprocessing techniques.

6 Results

6.1 Comparison of Preprocessing Techniques

The effectiveness of various preprocessing methods was evaluated by comparing the training, validation, and test accuracies obtained from four distinct experimental setups. Table 1 summarizes the performance metrics across these preprocessing techniques:

Table 1: Comparison of Training, Validation, and Test Accuracy Across Different Preprocessing Methods

Technique	Training Accuracy (%)	Validation Accuracy (%)	Test Accuracy (%)
EEG Preprocessing Without ASR (Experiment 1)	85.94	70.51	68.46
EEG Preprocessing ICA(ALL Files) + ASR(Noisy files only) (Experiment 2)	85.89	71.37	68.85
EEG Preprocessing No Epoching Before ICA (Experiment 3)	85.13	72.65	69.23
EEG Preprocessing ICA + ASR (Experiment 4)	86.32	73.08	71.15

From the results, it is evident that Experiment 4, which utilized both ICA and ASR for preprocessing, yielded the highest test accuracy of 71.15%. This suggests that the combination of these two techniques effectively mitigates the influence of noise and artifacts in the EEG data, allowing the model to perform better on unseen data.

Interestingly, Experiment 3, which applied no epoching before ICA, demonstrated a competitive validation accuracy of 72.65%. However, the lower test accuracy of 69.23% suggests that the model may have overfitted to the training data, emphasizing the importance of structured data segmentation in preprocessing.

6.2 Impact of Bias Initialization on BiLSTM Forget Gate

Further investigation into the effects of bias initialization for the BiLSTM forget gate revealed notable differences in model performance between two settings. The training, validation, and test accuracies for these experiments are presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Comparison of Performance Metrics for Different Bias Initializations of the BiLSTM Forget Gate

Bias Initialization Technique	Training Accuracy (%)	Validation Accuracy (%)	Test Accuracy (%)
Initialize the bias of the forget gate to 1 (Experiment 4)	86.32	73.08	71.15
Initialize the bias of the forget gate to 0 (Experiment 5)	82.08	70.51	66.54

The results indicate that initializing the bias of the forget gate to 1 in Experiment 4 resulted in superior performance across all metrics, achieving a test accuracy of 71.15%. In contrast, initializing the bias to 0 in Experiment 5 led to a significant drop in performance, with a test accuracy of only 66.54%. This highlights the critical role of bias initialization in influencing the learning dynamics of the BiLSTM, as proper initialization can facilitate better retention of relevant information over time.

6.3 Consistency of Model Performance

It is important to note that the performance of the model remained consistent across different runs when applying both ICA and ASR to all files (Experiment 4). In multiple independent training sessions, the model consistently achieved a test accuracy in the range of 71-72%, demonstrating

the robustness of the preprocessing pipeline and model architecture. This consistency highlights the reliability of the approach in handling EEG signal classification.

Overall, these findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the chosen preprocessing techniques and the importance of bias initialization in enhancing model performance for EEG classification tasks. Further investigations could explore additional techniques and parameter tuning to continue improving the robustness of the model.

7 Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate the significant impact of preprocessing techniques on EEG signal classification performance, particularly when using CNN-BiLSTM models. Across the experiments, we observed that the combination of **ICA** and **ASR** consistently improved model performance, with Experiment 4 (ICA + ASR applied to all files) yielding the highest test accuracy. This suggests that removing artifacts using both ICA and ASR is an effective strategy for reducing noise and enhancing the quality of the EEG signals, which, in turn, boosts model performance.

The consistent performance of the model across different runs, particularly in the range of 71-72% test accuracy, further supports the robustness of this preprocessing pipeline. The application of both ICA and ASR seems to provide a stable improvement across various trials, indicating that this combination can reliably enhance the generalizability of deep learning models trained on EEG data.

7.1 Impact of Preprocessing Techniques

Preprocessing methods like ICA and ASR are crucial in mitigating the effect of noise and artifacts in EEG data, which is inherently noisy due to muscle movements, eye blinks, and other biological and external factors. By applying ICA, we aimed to isolate independent sources of signal, which helps in removing non-neural components such as EOG artifacts. ASR further assists by filtering out noisy segments of the data. The superior performance of Experiment 4 confirms the synergy between ICA and ASR in cleaning the EEG signals, leading to more meaningful feature extraction by the CNN-BiLSTM model.

In contrast, the performance degradation observed in Experiment 3 (where no epoching was applied before ICA) underscores the importance of structured segmentation (epoching) of EEG data before performing artifact removal. Without epoching, the variability in the raw data likely introduced more noise, reducing the ability of ICA to effectively separate signals and artifacts.

7.2 Importance of Bias Initialization

In Experiment 5, we explored the impact of bias initialization on the BiLSTM forget gate. The results showed that initializing the bias of the forget gate to zero led to a slight decrease in performance compared to initializing it to one. This outcome aligns with findings from previous studies, which suggest that bias initialization can influence how quickly the BiLSTM model forgets previous states and learns new information. By initializing the bias to one, the forget gate is encouraged to retain more information in the initial stages of training, which may benefit sequential data like EEG signals where long-term dependencies are crucial.

7.3 Application to Future EEG Classification Tasks

The insights gained from this study can be applied to future EEG classification tasks. Preprocessing techniques like ICA and ASR should be considered as standard steps for artifact removal in EEG analysis. Additionally, bias initialization in BiLSTM models presents an opportunity to further

optimize model performance. This can be extended to other time-series data beyond EEG, where sequential patterns and dependencies are critical for classification.

8 Conclusion

In this study, we explored the impact of various preprocessing techniques and model optimization strategies on EEG signal classification using a CNN-BiLSTM-CNN-BiLSTM architecture. Our experiments demonstrated that preprocessing methods, particularly the combination of Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR), play a critical role in mitigating noise and enhancing the quality of EEG data. Notably, the implementation of proper epoching before applying ICA was found to be crucial, as it allowed for more structured data segmentation and helped stabilize the signals. This step ensured that ICA could effectively isolate artifacts, leading to cleaner EEG data. The combined use of epoching, ICA, and ASR across the dataset consistently improved model performance, resulting in more accurate and robust classification results.

Furthermore, our exploration of BiLSTM bias initialization, specifically within the forget gate, highlighted the importance of tuning model parameters to achieve optimal performance. Initializing the bias to one led to better retention of information in sequential data, which proved beneficial in classifying EEG signals, emphasizing the need for careful consideration of model initialization techniques.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of effective preprocessing and parameter optimization in EEG classification tasks. By addressing noise in the data and refining model architecture, we can significantly enhance the performance of deep learning models for EEG signal analysis, paving the way for future improvements in brain-computer interface systems and other related fields.

9 Code Availability

The code for reproducing the experiments and the dataset used in this paper are provided as a supplementary ZIP file with the submission. To use the code, follow these steps:

1. Download and extract the zip file from here: [Download Zip File](#).
2. Ensure you have the necessary Python environment as described in the "README.md".
3. Run the provided Jupyter notebooks or Python scripts.

10 Future Work

There are several avenues for potential future research based on the findings of this study. One possible direction is to explore alternative neural network architectures that may better capture the intricate patterns in EEG data. Architectures such as Transformer models or hybrid deep learning frameworks could offer enhanced performance compared to the CNN-BiLSTM structure used in this study.

In terms of preprocessing, more advanced techniques beyond ICA and ASR could be explored to further mitigate noise and improve signal quality. Methods such as Riemannian geometry-based filtering or more sophisticated artifact removal approaches could provide additional insights into optimizing EEG signal classification.

Furthermore, the impact of bias initialization in BiLSTM models could be studied in greater depth. Future work could explore adaptive or dynamic initialization methods that evolve throughout the

training process, potentially improving the model's ability to generalize across varying datasets. Expanding the study to other EEG datasets with different characteristics and noise profiles could also help validate the robustness of the proposed methods and further refine them for broader applications.

Finally, integrating domain knowledge from neuroscience or signal processing into the model design and training process may lead to better-informed models, resulting in more accurate EEG signal classification. These improvements could open up new possibilities in brain-computer interfaces and related applications.

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